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Effects of TikTok on Learner's Behavior

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Abstract – The study aimed to determine the effects of TikTok on learners' behavior at St. Paul University Surigao. Specifically, the study determined the impact of TikTok on learners' behavior in terms of moral entertainment, publicity, learning new things, and providing new things. The research-made questionnaire was administered to the Grade 12 students at St. Paul University Surigao. The statistical tool used was Frequency and Count Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The gathered data were statistically tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. Based on the findings of the study, the conclusions are offered: TikTok had highly effect on students learning behavior on moral entertainment, publicity, learning new things, and providing new things. In addition, the effects of TikTok on learning behavior were not influenced by the student's strand and time spent using the application. Based on the analysis and interpretations done on the data gathered, the different findings in this study were summarized as follows: (1) As to the participants' profile, most of the students were from HUMSS (48%) and most of them spent 1-2 hours (62%) in using TikTok; (2) Effects of TikTok on learners' behavior; (3) TikTok had highly effect in moral entertainment in interacting with creative challenges in making dances for other to recreate and have fun ($M=3.12$, $SD=1.10$); (4) TikTok had highly effect in publicity about the community guidelines of TikTok ($M=3.12$, $SD=1.00$); (5) TikTok had highly effect in learning new things in expanding their knowledge through educational videos ($M=3.16$, $SD=0.96$); (6) TikTok had highly effect in offering a lot of tools for creativity ($M=3.10$, $SD=0.91$); (7) There is no significant difference in the effects of TikTok on learners' behavior and their profile variables in terms of strand in moral entertainment, publicity, learning new things, and providing new things (p -values=0.538, 0.790, 0.087, 0.167, respectively), and time spent in TikTok in moral entertainment, publicity, learning new things, and providing new things (p -values=0.167, 0.897, 0.150, 0.068, respectively).

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Introduction

Rationale of the Study

Since the creation of TikTok, there has been a rapid increase in the use of such applications by teenagers in order to gain popularity and help ease boredom. Byte Dance owns the app, which was developed in China. The advanced app, formerly known as Musically, now has 500 million monthly active users, has 150 marketplaces, and is accessible in 75 languages. Previous research has found that image-focused apps can lead to a variety of mental health issues such as body dissatisfaction, eating disorders, narcissistic personalities, and so on. Child pornography, cyberbullying, and parental disengagement have all resulted from the use of this application. The paper employs a pragmatic approach to investigate the reasons for TikTok's sudden and massive success among teenagers, as well as its positive and negative effects. Content analysis is performed on the views and comments left by parents in the app store as feedback for downloading this application.

TikTok is one of the most popular apps on social media. This app is the world's prominent destination for creating short-form mobile videos in Asia, the United States, and other parts of the world. TikTok, also known as Douyin in China, started in September 2016 and is maintained by Byte Dance (Hallanan, 2018). People are investing more and more enthusiasm on the Internet as digital media grows in popularity. Trends, on the other hand, are always transient. Teenagers, who make up the majority of TikTok users, now have a new way to express themselves on social.

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Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Study Framework

This study was anchored on the concepts of Sirmin's effects of Tiktok on learner's behavior.

Based on Sirmin's (2020) concept, there are four effects of TikTok on the students, namely: (a) moral entertainment; TikTok is interactive, with creative challenges and dances people make for others to recreate and have fun with, (b) publicity; with TikTok, anyone can create short videos of themselves doing whatever they want that is appropriate and legal in order to titillate the public's interest and go viral in society, (c) learning new things; aside from funny and dancing videos, some people create videos with incredible opportunities and life tips that can benefit a large number of people, (d) providing new opportunities; with the ongoing pandemic, young students, such as high school students, have been using TikTok to find remote volunteering and internship opportunities (Simrin, 2020).

Reflected in figure 1 illustrates the Schematic Diagram of the study consisting of the dependent and independent variables: The first box presents the Profile of the participants, namely: age, strand, and time spent using TikTok.

Strand. It refers to the track and number of years of studying in a particular school (Merriam-Webster Dictionary). It is considered a variable in this study because it can determine the effects of TikTok on learners' behavior.

Time spent in using TikTok. It refers to the time of using TikTok for the participants. It is considered one of the variables in this study to know how long they spent their time using TikTok.

The second box in figure 1 presents the effects of TikTok on learner's behavior, namely: moral entertainment, publicity, learning new things, and providing new things.

Moral Entertainment. It refers to a principle concerning the distinction between right and wrong. TikTok's main benefit is that it is a terrific source of amusement. Users may dance, perform, and broaden their social circle on TikTok. TikTok is participatory, with users creating inventive challenges and dances for others to emulate and enjoy. It also delivers consistent, engaging material. Generally, TikTok is a fantastic tool for being engaged, especially amid the pandemic's stress (Sirmin, 2020).

Publicity. It refers to an active device to attract public interest, information with news value issued to gain public attention or support. TikTok is an excellent app for people who want to get famous for their unique talents and daring. With TikTok, anyone can create short videos doing anything they choose to do, appropriate and legal, to ensnare the public interest and become viral in society (Sirmin, 2020).

Learning New Things. It refers to helping the students to get new and knowledge-based perspectives around them. On top of the funny videos and the dancing videos, some people make videos with incredible opportunities and life tips that can help many people. Also, there are other people like doctors or teachers on TikTok utilizing the platform to teach new things every day (Sirmin, 2020).

Providing New Things. It refers to exploring new things, giving or supplying with something for their use or benefit. With the ongoing pandemic, young students such as high schoolers have found remote volunteering and internship opportunities directly from TikTok. As an engaging

platform, TikTok connects determined youths to volunteer for nonprofits like Linens N Love or intern for companies (Sirmin, 2020).

The third box in figure 1 presents the desired interventions on The Effects of TikTok on Learners Behavior of St. Paul University Surigao.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the Effects of TikTok on Learner’s Behavior at St. Paul University Surigao. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 strand; and
 - 1.2 time spent on TikTok?
2. What is the effect of TikTok on learning behavior of the students in terms of:
 - 2.1 moral entertainment;
 - 2.2 publicity;
 - 2.3 learning new things; and
 - 2.4 providing new things?
3. Is there a significant difference between the effects of TikTok on the learner’s behavior and their profile variables?
4. What are the proposed recommendations on the effects of TikTok on learners’ behavior of St. Paul University Surigao?

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study determines the profile of the senior high school students and the effects of TikTok on their learning behavior.

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

Profile	f (50)	%
Strand		
STEM	9	18
HUMSS	24	48
ABM	10	20
TVL	7	14
Time Spent in Using TikTok		
1-2 hours	31	62
3-4 hours	12	24
5-6 hours	2	4
6 or more	5	10

Table 1 shows the profile of the participants in terms of strand, and time spent in using TikTok. As to the strand of the participants, 24 or 48% are *HUMSS* students; 10 or 20% are *ABM* students; 9 or 18% are *STEM* and 7 or 14% are *TVL*. This only shows that most respondents are *HUMSS* students followed by *ABM*, *STEM* AND *TVL*, respectively.

As to the time spent in using TikTok, 31 or 62% are spending 1-2 hours; 12 or 24% are spending 3-4 hours; 5 or 10% are spending 6 or more and 2 or 4% are spending 5-6 hours. This only shows that they spent approximately 1-2 hours in using TikTok. As mentioned by Business of Apps (2019), when it comes to TikTok usage, users spend an average of 52 minutes per day on the app. This means that people are using the social networking app daily to create and share short videos of themselves or to watch TikTok videos already uploaded to the platform. In any case, they are doing it for nearly an hour every day.

Table 2 shows the effect of TikTok on learners' behavior of St. Paul University Surigao.

Table 2.

The Effects of TikTok on Learning Behavior of the Students in Moral Entertainment

A. MORAL ENTERTAINMENT	M	SD	VI	QD
1. TikTok is a global entertainment platform connecting communities over shared passions and interests.	3.08	1.08	A	E
2. TikTok can help me feel more accepted.	2.70	0.89	A	E
3. I have the ability to recognize which concepts are morally worth pursuing and which are not	2.88	1.00	A	E
4. TikTok is interactive, with creative challenges in which I make dances for others to recreate and have fun with.	3.12	1.10	A	E
5. I can easily discover its features and create content that shows positive vibes.	3.08	1.01	A	E
Average	2.97	1.02	A	E

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	SA	<i>Highly Effect</i>	HE
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Agree</i>	A	<i>Effect</i>	E
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Disagree</i>	D	<i>Less Effect</i>	LE
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	SD	<i>No effect</i>	NE

In *moral entertainment*, it can be ascertained that the indicator *TikTok is interactive, with creative challenges in which I make dances for others to recreate and have fun with* got the highest mean (M=3.12, SD=1.10), which is verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *highly effect*. This means that the learners find that TikTok is interactive, and they enjoy using the app. According to Aisha Malik (2022), TikTok announced this week that interactive add-ons are now available globally for in-feed ads to help brands create more engaging ads on its platform, it offers a way to engage with users through popups, stickers, and other visual elements. Meanwhile the indicator *TikTok can help me feel more accepted* got the lowest mean (M=2.70, SD=0.89) which is verbally interpreted as *agree* and qualitatively described as *effect*. This means that the learners feel the value of acceptance. As stated by Nielsen (2020), people do not have to be perfect, and that is perfect. Everyone belongs to the

TikTok community and is accepted. You are not only accepted but celebrated for being yourself by your viewers and fellow creators.

Table 3 shows the effect of TikTok on learners' behavior of St. Paul University Surigao.

Table 3.

The Effects of TikTok on Learning Behavior of the Students in Publicity

B. PUBLICITY	M	SD	VI	QD
1. The advertisement showed me a way to cope with the dangers at intersection of TikTok	2.98	0.77	A	E
2. I am comfortable posting videos on TikTok	2.52	0.99	A	E
3. I find TikTok very helpful for posting videos such as educational purposes	3.00	0.83	A	E
4. I avoid uploading malicious content.	3.10	1.07	A	E
5. I am aware of the community guidelines of TikTok	3.12	1.00	A	E
Average	2.94	0.93	A	E

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	SA	<i>Highly Effect</i>	HE
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Agree</i>	A	<i>Effect</i>	E
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Disagree</i>	D	<i>Less Effect</i>	LE
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	SD	<i>No effect</i>	NE

In *publicity*, the indicator *I am aware of the community guidelines of TikTok* got the highest mean (M=3.12, SD= 1.00) which is verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *highly effect*. This means that the learners are well informed with the community guidelines provided by TikTok. As stated by Cormac Keenan (2022) people should be able to express themselves creatively and be entertained in a safe, secure, and welcoming environment, according to TikTok. Our community guidelines help with this by establishing a set of standards so that people know what types of content to create on our platform and viewers know what to report to us. Our policies are intended to foster an environment that values safety, inclusion, and authenticity that they consider emerging trends observe on the internet platforms.

Meanwhile the indicator *I am comfortable posting videos on TikTok*, got the lowest mean (M=2.52, SD=0.99) which is verbally interpreted as *agree* and qualitatively described as *effect*. This implies that some of the learners of St. Paul University Surigao are comfortable in posting videos on TikTok. Thus, the learners are more confident in sharing their creativity using the app. Southern (2021), stated that TikTok users are at ease on the platform and even eager to interact with one another that the theme of positivity and users enjoyed their time on TikTok because they are delighted by the unique content they discover and feels safe expressing themselves through their own content.

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Table 4 shows the effect of TikTok on learners' behavior of St. Paul University Surigao.

Table 4.

The Effects of TikTok on Learning Behavior of the Students in Learning New Things

C. LEARNING NEW THINGS		M	SD	VI	QD
1.	TikTok assists me in coming up with new concepts.	3.10	0.84	A	E
2.	TikTok teach me something new, life hacks and shortcut.	3.08	0.97	A	E
3.	I can learn new dance move in by watching TikTok.	2.96	0.92	A	E
4.	TikTok enables me to learn about video editing such as basic cutting, audio precisions, transitions and more.	3.02	0.91	A	E
5.	TikTok expands my knowledge through educational videos.	3.16	0.96	A	E
Average		3.06	0.92	A	E

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	SA	<i>Highly Effect</i>	HE
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Agree</i>	A	<i>Effect</i>	E
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Disagree</i>	D	<i>Less Effect</i>	LE
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	SD	<i>No effect</i>	NE

In *learning new things*, it can be ascertained that the indicator *TikTok expands my knowledge through educational videos* got the highest mean (M=3.16, SD=0.96) which is verbally interpreted as *strongly agree* and qualitatively described as *highly effect*. This means that the learners of St. Paul University Surigao, TikTok helps expand their knowledge through watching educational videos and it is beneficial for them. According to Fanbytes (2022), TikTok has previously partnered with educational institutions, such as the initiative EduTok in India, which gained 126.5 billion views on videos across education, motivation and wellness.

Meanwhile the indicator *I can learn new dances move by watching TikTok* got the lowest mean (M=2.96, SD=0.92) which is verbally interpreted as *agree* and qualitatively described as *effect*. This means that the learners can catch up with the new trends. According to Halili (2019), TikTok dances have become increasingly popular owing to the need to exercise social separation and abundance of free time during quarantine that through movement and synchronization dance, dancing is beneficial to both physical and mental health.

Table 5 shows the effect of TikTok on learners' behavior of St. Paul University Surigao.

Table 5.

The Effects of TikTok on Learning Behavior of the Students in Providing New Things

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D. PROVIDING NEW THINGS	M	SD	VI	QD
1. TikTok offers a lot of tools for creativity.	3.10	0.91	A	E
2. TikTok helps me to learn different cultures in different countries	2.94	0.89	A	E
3. I can learn different types of language in TikTok.	2.94	0.89	A	E
4. TikTok helps me in providing my daily needs.	2.70	1.07	A	E
5. TikTok provides sponsorship to boost someone's small business	2.86	0.99	A	E
Average	2.91	0.95	A	E
Overall Average:	2.97	0.96	A	E

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Code	Qualitative Description	Code
4	3.25-4.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	SA	<i>Highly Effect</i>	HE
3	2.50-3.24	<i>Agree</i>	A	<i>Effect</i>	E
2	1.75-2.49	<i>Disagree</i>	D	<i>Less Effect</i>	LE
1	1.00-1.74	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	SD	<i>No effect</i>	NE

In *providing new things*, it can be ascertained that the indicator *TikTok offers a lot of tools for creativity* got the highest mean ($M=3.10$, $SD=0.91$) which is verbally interpreted as *agree* and qualitatively described as *effect*. This means TikTok provides a lot of tools that can improve the creativeness to the learners. According to TikTok (2019), they promote creativity and originality through their platform, and seen videos from all walks of life succeed on the app. TikTok is a groundbreaking short-form video platform that is powered and sustained by its users' positive creative expression. The app's entire reason for being is joyful, irreverent, witty, and entertaining user-generated content, which turns out to be the key to its enormous popularity. The opportunity for marketers in incorporating TikTok into the media mix is its unparalleled ability to reach large audiences on a new canvas, via a new breed of creative and authentic brand communications. It provides a massive tool for creators to be creative and experiment, it assists new artists in being discovered and existing artists in being rediscovered, and it provides a huge opportunity for creativity and audience engagement for brands (Creative Review, 2022).

Meanwhile the indicator *TikTok helps me in providing my daily needs* got the lowest mean ($M=2.70$, $SD=1.07$) which is verbally interpreted as *agree* and qualitatively described as *effect*. This implies that TikTok support the daily needs of the learners when it comes their studies and day to day living. According to Glebereport (2021), the app has gradually become more integrated into society and people's lives, and it has now begun to influence politics. TikTok has an impact on the economy in a variety of ways. For starters, having a social-media presence and platform is now a full-time job for some teenagers and young adults. On the overall average, the effect of TikTok on learners' behavior got the mean ($M=2.97$, $SD=0.96$) which is verbally interpreted as *agree* and qualitatively described as *effect*. This means that TikTok has an effect to the learners of St. Paul University Surigao when it comes to moral entertainment, publicity, learning and providing new things.

Table 6 shows the summary of Tables 2, 3, 4, and 5 on the Effects of TikTok on Learner's Behavior.

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Table of Summary

Effects of TikTok on Students Learning Behavior	Mean	QD
Moral Entertainment	2.97	E
Publicity	2.94	E
Learning new things	3.06	E
Providing new things	2.91	E

The *learning new things* got the highest mean of 3.06 which is qualitatively described as an *effect*. In contrast, the *providing new things* got the lowest mean of 2.91 which is qualitatively described as an *effect*.

Difference on the Effect of TikTok on Learning Behavior of the Students as to Profile

Table 7 shows the difference on the effect of TikTok on learning behavior of the students in St. Paul University Surigao.

Table 7.

Difference on the Effect of TikTok on Learning Behavior of the Students as to Profile

STRAND	SS Effect	df Effect	MS Effect	F	p-value	Decision
Moral Entertainment	1.698	3	.566	.732	.538	Do not reject H_0
Publicity	.557	3	.186	.349	.790	Do not reject H_0
Learning New Things	4.344	3	1.448	2.325	.087	Do not reject H_0
Providing New Things	3.167	3	1.056	1.767	.167	Do not reject H_0

TIME SPENT USING TIKTOK	SS Effect	df Effect	MS Effect	F	p-value	Decision
Moral Entertainment	3.850	3	1.283	1.766	.167	Do not reject H_0
Publicity	.319	3	.106	.198	.897	Do not reject H_0
Learning New Things	3.565	3	1.188	1.857	.150	Do not reject H_0
Providing New Things	4.363	3	1.454	2.544	.068	Do not reject H_0

p-value < 0.05; Reject H_0

The finding shows that there is no significant difference on the effect of Tiktok on learners' behavior to their strand in terms of moral entertainment (p-value=0.538), publicity (p-value=0.790), learning new things (p-value=0.087) and providing new things (p-value=0.167).

Additionally, there is no significant difference between the effects of TikTok on the learner's behavior and to the time spent in using TikTok in terms of moral entertainment (p-value=0.167), publicity (p-value=0.897), learning new things (p-value=0.150) and providing new things (p-value=0.068). It means that effects of TikTok to the learning behavior of the students is not influenced by the strand and time spent in using TikTok.

Results showed that there is no significant difference on the effect of TikTok on learning behavior of the students as to their profile variables. This only means that regardless of their strand and the time they spent on TikTok, the effects of TikTok towards the students are the same. Additionally, this indicate that the time spent on the application does not cause any changes in the student's study habits. This also shows that students have control on how much time they spend on the application itself. Seeing that there is no substantial change in the student's study habit means that they had control over what they are doing.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it is concluded that there is a high effect of TikTok on students learning behavior be it on moral entertainment, publicity, learning new things, and providing new things. In addition, the effects of TikTok on learning behavior were not influenced by the student's strand and time spent using the application.

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